

Reflectance analysis of the Otto chip using an automated reflectometer

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Abstract—This paper reports an experimental study focused on the characterization of the Otto chip device. These devices are structures sealed with a glass window, having a gold film, which is separated from the window surface by a well-defined gap. The gap is designed for the surface plasmon resonance effect. In this study, gap profiles were scanned by optical reflectometry. A preliminary analysis of reflectance curve patterns allows mapping the topography of the different regions of the chip. The results of the study can be used to optimize the manufacturing process of this type of structure.

Keywords— *Otto chip, SPR, sensors, optical profilometry, reflectometry*

I. INTRODUCTION

Surface plasmons (SP) are electromagnetic waves that propagate at the interface of a metal and a dielectric [1]. The SP is characterized by the confinement of the wave and it can be observed experimentally as a decreased intensity of the reflected wave [2]. There are several configurations in which surface plasmon resonance (SPR) is observed, such as diffraction gratings, thin films used in the Kretschmann configuration and the Otto configuration [2-4].

The SPR phenomena is used in the construction of sensors due to the high sensitivity to changes in optical characteristics of the media. The Otto configuration is still rarely used when compared to the Kretschmann configuration, but it has potential advantages in performance relative to the latter. In our previous study, an Otto chip device was conceived, fabricated, characterized and proposed for optical sensing applications [5]. The present work reports a first experimental study of the profile over the active area (metal film surface) of the Otto chip, by optical reflectometry.

II. METHODOLOGY

An excitation of SP is observed from the variation of intensity of the reflected wave as a function of an incidence angle θ . In the Otto configuration, shown in Fig. 1 [4], a prism is used

to allow SP excitation by an increased wave number of the incident laser [3].

Fig. 1. Otto configuration for excitation of surface plasmons.

The characterization of the optical device is performed by analyzing the reflectance of the structure. The reflectance in the configuration shown in Fig. 1 can be obtained by the Fresnel formulation for two interfaces with prism, dielectric and metal [6]. The thickness d , shown in Fig. 1, is thin enough for the evanescent wave to reach the dielectric-metal interface by exciting the SP. The Otto configuration allows the use of a thick metallic film, guaranteeing properties similar to those of the volumetric material.

The experimental curves are obtained using an automated reflectometer, the schematic diagram of which is shown in Fig. 2. In this study, we have used an Otto chip which consists of a 300 nm-thick gold film and a quartz window with an air-gap distance of 2.2 μm [5]. The Otto chip is placed on a prism in contact with a quartz window using an index matching oil. The reflectometer is capable of operating in sweeping mode, measuring surface points on the gold film spaced 2 mm apart in two orthogonal directions. The scanning angular range is 12 degrees with a resolution of 0.005 degrees at each point

measured at the surface. During the angular sweep, for a given measuring point, the reflectometer automatically adjusts so that the point illuminated by the laser remains stationary [7]. The point of illumination of the laser occupies an elliptical region on the surface of approximately 1.4 mm x 1 mm. A laser with a wavelength of $\lambda = 975.1$ nm is used. The light beam is polarized in the plane of incidence through a polarizer. Part of the beam is reflected by the splitter S and detected by the photodetector D_1 as a reference signal. The transmitted beam reaches the prism and is reflected being detected by D_2 .

Fig. 2. Automated reflectometer diagram.

III. RESULTS

With the automated reflectometer, a scanning experiment was carried out to map different parts of the gold film where the SP resonance is observed. Five measurement points were selected along the square area of 1 cm x 1 cm, patterns of reflectance curves were recorded, as indicated in Fig.3.

Fig. 3. Experimental reflectance curves for different laser footprint locations on the Otto chip surface.

In Fig. 3, the reflectance curves correspond to the laser illumination point on the gold surface, as indicated in the inset diagram of Fig. 3. In order to compare the measured SPR curves of different areas on the gold film, reflectance curves were measured at 5 points. The experimental curves infer a surface topography of the gold film and clearly show the similar SPR effect with slight discrepancy, except in the case of point 4, which is located on the edge of the gold surface. The absence of the clear SPR effect means that the measured signal at point 4 is a mix between reflectances at the silicon and gold surface.

Reference [8] shows a video generated in the scope of this work, with the complete scanning of the Otto chip, showing more clearly the variation of the reflectance curve according to laser footprint position. In particular, it was possible to characterize from the SPR curves the entire region occupied by the 1 cm x 1 cm gold film, measured as a set of 25 curves.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The results show that the analyzed Otto chip exhibits a gap region, where the active region is metallized with a reasonably uniform gold film. The slight variation in gap thickness across the metallized area is being analyzed, based on non-linear regression of the experimental data. Scan studies of the type reported here are important in order to improve the manufacturing process of this class of devices for future technological applications.

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